

Interface specifications for existing EHRs

Milestone n. 5

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Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

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1. Document overview

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the technical specifications regarding the data transfer from the hospital information systems already in use in the EDs involved in the eCREAM project and the eCREAM platform. In particular, it describes the list of parameters to be extracted from hospital systems defined according to a Data dictionary that has been defined analysing the needs for information. The document also outlines the methods by which this information will be extracted from the systems and transferred to the eCREAM infrastructure, how it will be processed, and the infrastructural solution.

The document will address the project scopes with particular focus on the following ones:

- NLP training: Development of a Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool to enable the extraction of clinical variables from text in medical reports.
- Use Case 1: Assessing the propensity of ED to hospitalise patients.
- Use case 2: Development of a multifunctional dashboard for real-time monitoring of emergency departments.

Not all the hospitals are committed to take part to the NLP training, however they are required to participate in the other two use cases.

1.2. Mapping between the needed dataset and the hospitals available data

1.2.1. Data to be collected from the hospital information systems

For the achievement of the different project objectives, different types of information have been identified:

- NLP Training: the NLP must be trained on textual information to be exported from ED EHR and RIS database, e.g., medical history, medical examination, radiology test report. Data must belong to all the patients assisted by the EDs during the period 2021-2023. Before the NLP training ingestion, all the text will be anonymized, will lose their linkage to the patient and, consequently, the linkage to each other. Working on these texts, the NLP will be trained to extract clinical variables to be used in UC1.
- UC1: The data to be collected by the hospitals must refer only to adult patients cared in the period 2021-2023, with assessment of dyspnea or temporary loss of consciousness, and can be of two types:
 - organizational type (logistical and non-clinical), gathered as a structured dataset, that are useful for evaluating the crowding level the emergency department during the clinical activities;
 - clinical type, gathered as structured and textual dataset. The texts containing the clinical information will be the same used for the NLP training, but this time they will have linkage to the patient and therefore to each other.
- UC2: The needed data are solely of a logistic type, in real time for all patients assisted in the EDs since this use case collection starts.

1.2.2. NLP training use case – needed information

The textual data that can provide the values for the UC1 variables are listed here:

- Anamnesis
- Clinical examination
- Home-based therapy
- Clinical diary
- Nursing notes
- Clinical condition at discharge
- Diagnosis at end of hospital stay
- Discharge notes
- Allergies (triage)
- Drugs taken at home (triage)
- Known pathologies collected at triage
- Description of event at triage
- Other triage notes
- Imaging examination reports and other tests (e.g., stress test)
- Specialist consultations

Some of these data can be archived in the EHR database, other can be stored in the RIS database, according to the hospital policies.

1.2.3. UC1 – needed information

UC1 will need the following information

Logistical data

- Date and time of arrival at the ED
- Triage Priority
- Date and time of triage
- Date and time of collection of vital parameters
- Date and time of nurse's taking charge of the patient
- Date and time of doctor's taking charge of the patient
- Date and time of specialistic visit request and execution
- Date and time of laboratory test request and execution
- Date and time of radiology test request, execution and report
- Date and time of visit
- Date and time of the decision to transfer to Observation Unit
- Date and time of the decision to admit/transfer to another hospital/discharge,
- Date and time of transfer to Observation Unit
- Date and time of exit from ED/ Observation Unit
- Mode of exit (admitted/transferred/deceased/voluntary abandonment)
- Date and time of patient discharge from the ER.

Clinical data DISPNEA

History taking

- History of allergy
- History of recent trauma
- Pregnancy
- Presence of chronic pulmonary disease (either obstructive or restrictive)
- Chronic organ failure (respiratory, cardiac, renal, metabolic)
- Diffuse vascular disease
- Chronic rheumatologic disease
- Active neoplasia
- Chronic dialysis
- Immunosuppression
- Palliative care
- Neuropsychiatric disorders
- Poly-pharmacological therapy
- Problematic family context
- Need but absence of a caregiver
- Homelessness
- Living alone

Clinical examination

- Dementia
- General condition deterioration
- Level of autonomy (mobility)
- Level of consciousness
- Agitation
- Presence of respiratory distress
- Foreign body in the airways
- Respiratory rate
- Body temperature
- Heart rate
- Blood pressure
- Improvement of dyspnea

Lab test results

- SpO₂
- pH
- PaO₂
- PaCO₂
- HCO₃⁻
- Lactates
- Hemoglobin
- Platelets

- Leukocytes
- C-Reactive Protein
- Blood sodium
- Blood potassium
- Blood glucose
- Creatinine
- Transaminases
- INR
- Troponin
- BNP / NT-pro-BNP
- D-dimer
- SARS-CoV-2 swab test

Imaging test results

- Thoracic ultrasound, any abnormalities
- ECG, any abnormalities
- Head/neck CT, any abnormalities
- Chest CT, any abnormalities
- Chest Rx, any abnormalities

Treatment

- Performance of thoracentesis
- Administration of diuretics
- Administration of steroids
- Administration of bronchodilators
- Administration of oxygen/ventilation
- Blood transfusions

Final diagnosis

- Pulmonary embolism
- Heart Failure
- Pneumonia
- Copd Exacerbation
- Acute Pulmonary Edema
- Asthma Exacerbation
- Severe anaemia
- Arrhythmia
- Respiratory Failure
- Intoxication
- COVID 19
- Influenza and various infections
- Pneumothorax
- Acute Coronary Syndrome

Clinical data TLoC

History taking

- History of drug abuse
- History of alcohol abuse
- Presence of pacemaker
- Presence of defibrillator
- Cardio-pulmonary resuscitation
- Antihypertensive therapy
- Anticoagulants or antiplatelet drug therapy
- Diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases
- Diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases
- Diagnosis of peripheral neuropathy
- Pregnancy
- Diagnosis of Chronic respiratory failure
- Diagnosis of Chronic cardiac failure
- Diagnosis of Chronic renal failure
- Diagnosis of Chronic metabolic failure
- Diagnosis of Diffuse vascular disease
- Diagnosis of Chronic rheumatologic disease
- Active neoplasia
- Chronic dialysis
- Immunosuppression
- Palliative care
- Neuropsychiatric disorders
- Poly-pharmacological therapy
- Speed with which the patient recovered consciousness
- Presence of prodromal symptoms
- Compliance with antiepileptic therapy
- Duration of the patient's unconsciousness
- TLoC during effort
- TLoC while supine
- First episode vs. known history of epilepsy
- Antiepileptic therapy already in place
- Drowsiness, confusion, disorientation as postcritical state
- Pale skin during the episode
- Eye deviation during the episode
- Stiffness during the episode
- Drooling during the episode
- Tonic-clonic seizures
- Situation description, like coughing, prolonged periods of straining, sudden abdominal pain, phlebotomy
- Problematic family context

- Need but absence of a caregiver
- Homelessness
- Living alone

Clinical examination

- Dementia
- General condition deterioration
- Level of autonomy (mobility)
- Level of consciousness
- Agitation
- Presence of dyspnea
- Body temperature
- Heart rate
- Blood pressure
- Chest pain
- Head or other districts trauma
- Ab ingestis pneumonia
- Tongue bite
- Further seizures in the ED
- Blood in the stool
- Carotid sinus massage
- Supine-to-standing systolic blood pressure test
- Improvement of patient's conditions
- Neurologist consultation

Diagnostic test results

- ECG, any abnormality
- ECG monitoring, any abnormality
- EEG, any abnormality

Lab test results

- SpO2
- Lactates
- Hemoglobin
- Platelets
- Leukocytes
- C-Reactive Protein
- Blood glucose
- Blood sodium
- Blood potassium
- Blood calcium
- Creatinine

- Transaminases
- INR
- Troponin
- BNP / NT-pro-BNP
- D-Dimer
- Serum creatine kinase
- Blood alcohol
- Blood drug dosage
- Urine drug test

Imaging test results

- Brain CT scan, any abnormality
- Brain MRI, any abnormality
- Cardiac ultrasound, any abnormality
- Chest CT scan, any abnormality
- Pulmonary scintigraphy, any abnormality
- Gastroscopy
- Abdomen CT scan, any abnormality
- Doppler ultrasound of deep veins, any abnormality
- Compression ultrasound (CUS), any abnormality

Treatment

- Administration of fluids

Final diagnosis

- Situational syncope
- Epilepsy / epileptic seizure
- Pulmonary embolism
- Arrhythmia
- Cardiac tamponade
- Aortic dissection
- Acute coronary syndrome
- Hemorrhage
- Severe Anaemia
- Concussive head trauma

Some information included in this list will be extracted by the NLP model from the textual information belonging to the types that have been described in the paragraph “2.1.1. NLP training – needed information”

1.2.4. UC2 – needed information

The information needed to perform this use case are:

- Date and time of arrival at the ED
- Mode of arrival (Ambulance, Autonomous (by own means), Helicopter, Other (fire department, military ambulance, etc.), Not noted)
- Age [number]
- Sex [male/female]
- Triage Priority
- Date and time of triage
- Date and time of collection of vital parameters
- Date and time of nurse's taking charge of the patient
- Date and time of doctor's taking charge of the patient
- Date and time of specialistic visit request and execution
- Date and time of laboratory test request and execution
- Date and time of radiology test request, execution and report
- Date and time of visit
- Date and time of the decision to transfer to Observation Unit
- Date and time of the decision to admit/transfer to another hospital/discharge,
- Date and time of transfer to Observation Unit
- Date and time of exit from ED/ Observation Unit
- Mode of exit (admitted/transferred/deceased/voluntary abandonment)
- Date and time of patient discharge from the ER.

1.3. Hospitals available data

In WP2, a technical questionnaire was used to know which data of eCREAM interest are collected by the participating hospitals on ED EHR/LIS/RIS and in which format.

The results of the questionnaires is available within the document "D2.1_Technological context".

These questionnaires showed that the format in which several data can be gathered differs from one hospital to another: structured, textual or both.

For example, vital signs in most cases are collected in precise structured fields but they are often included in textual fields and provided in descriptive form.

In order to provide the hospitals with the specification of the datasets to be exported from their database, a set data dictionaries have been defined. These data dictionaries are the same for all the hospitals because they comprehend all the several formats in which every needed information can be found in the hospital databases, both structured and textual.

2. Data dictionary definition

This chapter describes the data dictionaries as a mapping tool for the variables reported in the paragraph “2.1. Data to be collected from the hospital information systems “, and the data made available by the hospital systems. They represent the specification of the data (data naming, type, meaning, format, if mandatory requested, constraints) to be exported by the hospitals and transferred to the eCREAM platform.

The definition of the data dictionaries is guided by these criteria:

- the exportation of information in the various available formats, with minimum elaboration by the hospital
- the linkage of data that are present on different systems (e.g. radiology test requests recorded in the ED and their reports archived in the RIS)
- the tracking of events of the same kind that can occur more than once during an emergency episode (e.g. repetition of a specific laboratory examination or a radiology test during the diagnostic assessment or the clinical conditions monitoring).

The data dictionaries are specified according to the type of data, to the use case that needs those data and to the hospital information system that can provide them.

So, the defined data dictionaries are:

- NLP Training – ED EHR
- NLP Training – RIS
- UC1 - ED EHR
- UC1 – LIS
- UC1 - RIS
- UC2

Every data dictionary contains these data for all the information:

- **Subset Name:** It indicates the aggregation of a data subset
- **Field Name** - It indicates the detailed subfield whose field Entity 1 is aggregating. A field of type Entity 2 can be repeatable if it is a subfield of a List entity.
- **Definition:** Describes the meaning of the Field.
- **Type:** Describes the data type (string, integer, etc.).
- **Mandatory Field:** Indicates whether the field is mandatory, optional, or conditionally mandatory. Specifically:
 - **MANDATORY:** Field whose value is always required, failing which the data will not be validated.
 - **OPTIONAL:** Field whose value is not mandatory, but it is recommended to fill it whenever the data is present in the source application (e.g., 'DecisionObsUnit' is optional since not all cases in the Emergency Department result in a decision towards Observation Unit, but it is recommended to populate it for all cases that reach Observation Unit).
 - **CONDITIONALLY MANDATORY:** Field whose value is mandatory under specific conditions, as indicated in the field's definition (e.g., if the result field is filled then value's udm is mandatory).

- **Domain Information:** Contains additional detailed information about the requested data.
- **Example:** In some cases, an example of the type of information collected is provided.
- **UC1 Dyspnea, UC1 TLOC, and UC2:** Indicate the use case for which these data are required.

2.1. NLP Training – ED EHR

Below is the “NLP Training ED EHR data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
textual DataED						
	trriageNotes	trriage notes	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's other triage notes Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	Patient appears anxious and distressed
	anamnesis	anamnesis	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's medical history Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	allergiesTriage	allergies detected in triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's allergies Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	clinicalExamination	clinical examination	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical examination Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	knownPathologiesCollectedAtTriage	known pathologies collected at triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's known pathologies collected at triage	

					Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters	
	descriptionOfEventAtTriage	description of event at triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's description of event at triage Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	otherTriageNotes	other triage notes	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's other triage notes Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	vitalParameters	Vital parameters	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's vital parameters Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	homeBasedTherapy	home-based therapy	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's home based therapy Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	clinicalDiary	clinical diary	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical diary Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	medicalVisit	medical visit	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's medical visit Format: alphanumeric	

					string up to 4000 characters.	
	clinicalEDOutcome	clinical condition at discharge	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical condition at discharge Format: alphanumeric string to 4000 characters.	
	nursingNotes	nursing notes	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's nursing notes Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	clinicalConditionDischarge	clinical condition at discharge	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical condition at discharge Format: alphanumeric string to 4000 characters.	
	diagnosisAtEndOfHospitalStay	diagnosis at end of hospital stay	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's diagnosis at end of hospital stay Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	dischargeNotes	discharge notes	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's discharge notes Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	drugsTakenAtHome	drugs taken at home detected in triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's drugs taken at home (triage) Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	

	treatment	treatment	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's treatment Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	clinicalConditionAtDischarge	Clinical condition at discharge	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical condition at discharge Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	reportTextSpecialistConsultancy	report of consultations	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's information of consultations Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	EDDischargeCarePlan	ED Care Plan	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's information plan Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	

2.2. NLP Training – RIS

Below is the “NLP Training RIS data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
textualDataRIS						
	imagingTestReport	Imaging examination reports	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's imaging examination	the CT examination did not provide any additional

					report Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	data to what had already emerged
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2.3. UC1 ED EHR

Below is the “UC1 ED EHR data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
EDEpisode			EDEpisode	Mandatory	Admission of the patient to the ED.	
	EpisodeID	identification ED patient’s admission	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	231457
	EDArrivalDate Time	Date and time of arrival at the ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
triage			triage	Mandatory	Patient triage information.	
	triageDateTime	Date and time of triage.	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	triagePriority	Urgency level assigned to the patient and relative priority.	String	Mandatory	Allowed values: Code - Description: 1,2,3,4,5,6, X (Not performed)	2
	triageNotes	triage notes	String	Optional	triage notes Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters.	Patient appears anxious and distressed
	descriptionEventTriage	triage description	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding description of triage	

					Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	drugsTakenAt Home	Drugs taken at home detected in triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's drugs taken at home (triage) Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	
	allergiesTriag e	Allergies detected in triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's allergies. Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	None reported
	knownPathol ogiesCollecte dAtTriage	known pathologies collected at triage	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's known pathologies collected at triage Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters	
anamnesis			anamnes is	Mandatory	Set of patient medical history information	
	anamnesis	anamnesis collected at triage	String	Mandatory	the taking of a patient's personal medical history Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	Family history of heart disease

homeBasedTherapy			homeBasedTherapy	Optional		
	homeBasedTherapy	home-based therapy	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's home based therapy Format: alphanumeric string up to 4000 characters.	Penicillin
clinicalExamination			clinicalExaminationDetection	Optional	Clinical tests performed.	
	dateTimeDetection	Date and time of the patient's clinical examination detection upon entering the ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23
	clinicalExamination	clinical examinations carried out in ED	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters.	
imagingText			imagingTestExecutionList	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	dateTimeRequestImagingTest	Date and time of imaging test request	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeImagingTestExecution	Date and time of imaging test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	dateTimeImagingTestReport	Date and time of imaging test report	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:15:23

	imagingTestDescription	Description of imaging test	String	Mandatory	coded field with description of the laboratory test. If Dyspnoea: US, Head/neck CT, Chest CT, Chest Rx, if TLoC: Brain CT scan, Brain MRI, US cardiac, Chest CT scan, Pulmonary scintigraphy, Gastroscopy, Abdomen CT scan	
	imagingTestReportText	Report of the imaging tests (CT, CR,etc.).	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
labText			labTestExecution List	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	labTestDescription	description of laboratoryTest	String	Mandatory	coded field with description of the laboratory test. If Dyspnoea: pH,,PaO2 ,PaCO2 ,HCO3 ,Lactates ,Haemoglobin ,Platelets ,Leukocytes ,CReactiveProtein ,bloodGlucose ,bloodSodium ,bloodPotatium ,Creatinine ,Transaminases ,INR,Troponin,BN P,DDimer ,SARSCoV2swabTest	

					if TLoC: Lactates, Haemoglobin, Platelets, Leukocytes, CReactiveProtein, bloodGlucose, bloodSodium, bloodPotatium, bloodCalcium, Creatinine, Transaminases, INR, Troponin, BNP, DDimer, CreatineKinase, BloodAlcohol, BloodDrug, UrineDrug	
	dateTimeRequestLabTest	Date and time of laboratory test request	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeLabTestExecution	Date and time of laboratory test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	labTextResults	Results of laboratory test	decimal	Optional		
	unitOfMeasureLabText	result test measure unit	String	Mandatory Conditional	if NumericResults is valued. Allowed values, for example: mg/dL, g/dL, U/L, mmol/L, %, 10^12/L, 10^9/L, pg, fL, U/L, ratio, sec, INR	%
vitalParameters			vitalParametersDetectionList	Optional	List of patient vital signs. Populated with as many elements of the "vitalParameters" entity as there are patient data collections.	
	dateTimeDetection	Date and time of the patient's vital signs in ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23

	systolicPressure	Systolic pressure at triage	Integer	Mandatory	Integer value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure mmHg	100
	diastolicPressure	Diastolic pressure at triage.	Integer	Mandatory	Integer value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure mmHg	120
	heartRate	Heart rate at triage.	Integer	Mandatory	Integer value from 0 to 3 digits, unit of measure Bpm	75
	respiratoryRate	Respiratory rate at triage.	Integer	Mandatory	Integer value from 0 to 2 digits, unit of measure breaths/minute	18
	bodyTemperature	Body temperature at triage.	Decimal	Mandatory	Decimal value (2 digits, 1 digit after the separator) unit of measure degrees Celsius	38.3
	SpO2	Oxygen saturation detected at triage	Integer	Mandatory	Integer value to 2 digits	95
	vitalParametersText	information on vital parameters recorded during presence in ED	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 400 characters.	
nursingCareData		NursingCareData	nursingCareData	Optional	Nursing care of the patient.	
	dateTimePPCI	Date and time of nurse's taking on of the patient	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T1:13:23
	nursingNotes	nursing notes, Includes any procedures and treatments	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
medicalVisits			medicalVisit List	Mandatory Conditional	List of patient's medical visits	
	dateTimeMedicalVisit	Date and time of doctor's taking on of the patient:	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23

	medicalVisitOutcome	medical visit	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
clinicalDiary			clinicalDiary List	Optional		
	dateTimeClinicalDiary	Date and time of medical visit	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
	clinicalDiary	clinical diary Includes any procedures, treatments and known pathologies	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	Initiate ECG monitoring
specialistConsultancy			executionConsultation List	Optional	Specialist patient consultations. Filled with as many consultations as there are consultations performed.	
	dateTimeSpecialistConsultancy	Date and time of patient specialist consultancy	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23
	reportTextSpecialistConsultancy	report and outcome of the consultation	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
Discharge			finalDiagnosis	Optional	List final diagnosis. Populated with as many elements of the finalDiagnosisList entity as the final diagnoses.	
	dischargeDecisionDateTime	Date and time of the decision to admit/transfer to another	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23

		hospital/discharge, if the patient has to wait for a bed or a transfer to another hospital (boarding)				
	dischargeDateTime	Date and time of patient discharge from ED.	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	clinicalEDOutcome	patient's clinical course	String	Optional	Summary of information regarding the patient's clinical course, including clinical evaluations, short-term clinical goals, clinical notes. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
	EDDischargeCarePlan	care plan at the patient's discharge.	String	Optional	Includes general information of the clinical event concerning the care transition from the hospital setting to the territorial one. In this section, any recommended checks can also be described. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 500 characters.	
	EDDischargingPharmacologicalTherapy	pharmacologic al therapy to be performed on	String	Optional	Dedicated to describing all the medications that the patient should	

		the patient at discharge.			take at home. Format: Alphanumeric string up to 500 characters.	
	modeOfExit	Exit Mode	Integer	Optional	Allowed values:: 1- if admitted 2 - if transferred 3 - if decease 4 - if voluntary abandonment	2
	clinicalConditionDischarge	patient's clinical condition at the time of discharge from ED and diagnosis at end of hospital stay	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
	diagnosisAtEndOfHospitalStay	diagnosis at the end of hospitalisation	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
	DischargeNotes	discharge notes	String	Optional	Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.	
ObsUnit			Observation Unit	Optional	Set of information relating to the patient's presence in the Obs Unit	
	decisionObsUnit	Date and time of decision to transfer to Short Stay Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	transferObsUnit	Date and time of transfer to Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23

	exitObsUnit	Date and time of exit from ED/Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
followup			followup	Optional	Indicates 30-day mortality, detects if the patient is alive or deceased	
	30DayMortality	Indicates 30-day mortality, detects if the patient is alive or deceased	String	Optional	allowed values: yes/no/not detectable	No

2.4. UC1 LIS

Below is the “UC1 LIS data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
LabTest			LabTest List			
	EpisodeID	identification ED admission	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	
	requestID	laboratory examination request number	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 40 characters.	
	labTestDescription	lab Test description	String	Mandatory	coded field with description of the laboratory test. If Dyspnea: pH,,PaO2 ,PaCO2 ,HCO3 ,Lactates ,Hemoglobin ,Plateletsn ,Leukocytes ,CReactiveProtein ,bloodGlucose ,bloodSodium ,bloodPotatium ,Creatinine ,Transaminases	

					,INR,Troponin,BNP,DDimer ,SARSCoV2swabTest if TLoC: Lactates, Hemoglobin ,Platelets ,Leukocytes ,CReactiveProtein ,bloodGlucose ,bloodSodium ,bloodPotatium ,bloodCalcium ,Creatinine ,Transaminases,INR ,Troponin ,BNP ,DDimer ,CreatineKinase ,BloodAlcohol ,BloodDrug ,UrineDrug	
	dateTimeRequestLabTest	Date and time of the request for the lab test	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeLabTestExecution	Date and time of the lab test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	labTextResults	numeric Results of lab test	decimal	Optional	test result	
	unitOfMeasureLabText	Unit of measure for the result.	String	Mandatory Conditional	if NumericResults is valued. Allowed values, for example: mg/dL, g/dL, U/L, mmol/L ,%, 10^12/L, 10^9/L, pg, fL, U/L, ratio, sec, INR	%

2.5. UC1 RIS

Below is the “UC1 RIS data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
imagingText			imagingTestExecution List	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTest Execution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	EpisodeID	identification ED admission	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	
	requestID	radiology examination request number	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 40 characters.	
	dateTimeRequestImagingTest	Date and time of the request for imaging test	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeImagingTestExecution	Date and time of the execution of the imaging test	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
	dateTimeImagingTestReport	Date and time of the imaging test report	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:15:23

					<p>coded field with description of the laboratory test.</p> <p>If Dispnea: US, Head/neck CT, Chest CT, Chest Rx, if TLoC: Brain CT scan, Brain MRI, US cardiac, Chest CT scan, Pulmonary scintigraphy , Gastroscopy , Abdomen CT scan</p>	
	imagingTestDescription	Description of the imaging test	String	Mandatory		RX chest
	imagingTestReportText	report of the imaging tests (radiology, etc.).	String	Optional	<p>Format: Alphanumeric string up to 2000 characters.</p>	<p>No significant lesions are observed bony lesions of the skeletal segments under examination</p>

2.6. UC2

Below is the “UC2 data dictionary” contained in the “Annex 1 - eCREAM - Data dictionary”

SUBSET NAME	FILED NAME	Definition	Type	Mandatory Field	Domain Information	Example
EDEpisode			EDAccess	Mandatory	Admission of the patient to the ED.	
	EpisodeID	identification ED patient's admission	String	Mandatory	Alphanumeric string, maximum length: 20 characters.	231457
	EDArrivalDate Time	Date and time of arrival at the ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	sex	Gender of the patient	Integer	Mandatory	Allowed values: 1 for Male, 2 for Female, 9 for Not Specified	1
	age	The age in years of the patient	Integer	Mandatory		27
	arrivalModeCode	How the patient arrived at the ED: e.g. by ambulance dispatched by pre-hospital emergency service (EMS), by helicopter dispatched by EMS, transferred from an ED of another Hospital, Self-presented/by their own means,	Integer	Mandatory	Allowed values: 1: Ambulance 2: Autonomous (by own means) 3: Helicopter 4: Other (fire department, military ambulance, etc.) 5: Not known N.B. Other coding is allowed, provided that they can be traced back to the above items.	2
triage			triage	Mandatory	Patient triage information.	
	triageDateTime	Date and time of triage.	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:15:23

	triagePriority	Urgency level assigned to the patient and relative priority.	String	Mandatory	Allowed values: Code - Description: 1,2,3,4,5,6, X (Not performed)	
clinicalExamination			clinicalExaminationDetection	Optional	Clinical tests performed.	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeDetection	Date and time of the patient's clinical examination detection upon entering the ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:14:23
imagingText			imagingTestExecutionList	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	2022-06-22T15:15:23
	dateTimeRequestImagingTest	Date and time of imaging test request	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
	dateTimeImagingTestExecution	Date and time of imaging test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimeImagingTestReport	Date and time of imaging test report	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:14:23
labText			labTestExecutionList	Optional	Populated with as many elements of the imagingTestExecution entity as there are imaging tests.	
	dateTimeRequestLabTest	Date and time of laboratory test request	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:15:23
	dateTimeLabTestExecution	Date and time of laboratory test execution	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
vitalParameters			vitalParametersDetectionList	Optional	List of patient vital signs. Populated with as many elements of the	2022-06-22T1:13:23

					"vitalParameters" entity as there are patient data collections.	
	dateTimeDetection	Date and time of the patient's vital signs in ED	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	
nursingCareData		NursingCareData	nursingCareData	Optional	Nursing care of the patient.	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimePPCI	Date and time of nurse's taking on of the patient	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
medicalVisits			medicalVisitList	Mandatory Conditional	List of patient's medical visits. Populated with as many elements of the medicalVisits entity as there are patient visits. Mandatory if: 1. the dischargeDecision is "1-Home Discharge" 2. discharge with EsitoPS code ≠ 6 (The patient leaves the ED before the medical visit) or with EsitoPS code ≠ 9 (cadaver arrival). Values in the EDDischarge table.	
	dateTimeMedicalVisit	Date and time of doctor's taking on of the patient:	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
clinicalDiary			clinicalDiaryList	Optional		2022-06-22T15:15:23

	dateTimeClinicalDiary	Date and time of medical visit	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
specialist Consultancy			executionConsultation List	Optional	Specialist patient consultations. Filled with as many consultations as there are consultations performed.	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	dateTimespecialistConsultancy	Date and time of patient specialist consultancy	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss"	2022-06-22T15:13:23
Discharge			finalDiagnosis	Optional	List final diagnosis. Populated with as many elements of the finalDiagnosisList entity as the final diagnoses.	2
	dischargeDecisionDateTime	Date and time of the decision to admit/transfer to another hospital/discharge, if the patient has to wait for a bed or a transfer to another hospital (boarding)	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
	dischargeDateTime	Date and time of patient discharge from ED.	String	Mandatory	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	2022-06-22T15:13:23
	modeOfExit	Mode of exit	Integer	Mandatory	Allowed values:: 1- if admitted 2 - if transferred 3 - if decease 4 - if voluntary abandonment	2022-06-22T15:13:23
ObsUnit			ObservationUnit	Optional	Set of information relating to the	2022-06-22T15:13:23

					patient's presence in the Obs Unit	
	decisionObsUnit	Date and time of decision to transfer to Short Stay Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
	transferObsUnit	Date and time of transfer to Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	
	exitObsUnit	Date and time of exit from ED/Observation Unit	String	Optional	Date format: "YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss".	

3. Definition of the solution architecture

The image above identifies three main areas: Hospital, which includes the Local eCREAM components, Partners NLP Server, and Central eCREAM platform.

The data flows are designed accordingly to the constraints of the IP privacy protection, as they apply to the different use cases. So, the processing of data is distributed among those areas in order to be compliant with those constraints.

3.1. Local and Central eCREAM Infrastructure

The architecture of the eCREAM platform infrastructure and applications has been designed in order to fulfil the following criteria: IP data protection, security and service performance.

The eCREAM platform is composed of components installed within the hospital facilities (local eCREAM) and components installed on central servers (central eCREAM).

3.1.1. Local eCREAM

The local components have the main purpose of receiving and pre-processing hospital data before they are transferred to the central services.

The components are:

- **RESTful API** for the JSON message transfer in UC2
- **file systems** for the hospital data transfer in NLP training use cases and UC1
- **Anonymizer** tool that will erase patient’s identification data from the hospital textual notes gathered for NLP training and UC1
- **Pre-processing tool** for elaboration of measures to be used in the statistical analysis of logistical data, that is used for the ED crowding evaluation in UC1 and UC2
- **Database** for temporary local storage
- **Service for the text file transfer** to NLP training, that delete the linkage of the ED episodes from the files and send them to the training facilities
- **Service for the structured data transfer** to the central components.

Minimum requirements for hospital infrastructure

The local components will be included in a Docker instance that will be hosted in the hospital servers. The server can be a physical or a virtual one, depending on the hospital. The following minimum requirements are mandatory for the server:

- CPU: 16 Cores
- RAM: 32 GB
- Local Disk: 100 GB
- External Physical Disk: 500 GB

Additionally, each hospital must provide external VPN access to ensure Astir system administrators can access the Docker machine for the maintenance activities.

The Docker machine must also have the capability to connect externally to transfer data to the Central eCREAM component.

The exchange of necessary information from each institution to the Local eCREAM platform and the data that will be extracted and saved in a folder structure, as described above, will occur according to the instructions provided. Data will be saved in batch mode on an external physical disk connected to the Docker machine.

3.1.2. Central eCREAM

The central components will provide the final processing and presentation to the users of the data that have been gathered from the hospitals.

The central components are:

- **RESTful API** for data gathering from the local components
- **NLP tool** that will extract structured information from the textual file
- **Database**
- **Tool for the normalization** of the hospital data
- **Tool for the elaboration of the ED monitoring indicators**, including the crowding level used in UC1 and UC2 or the values that will be showed in the UC2 dashboard and in the citizen's mobile app
- **Tool for the elaboration of the propensity** of hospitalization
- **KPI Dashboard application** for hospitals and administrative offices
- **RESTful API** for transfer of real time data to the citizen's mobile app

The central components will be hosted in a cloud server farm that has the ISO 27018 certification (standard of practice for protection of personally identifiable information (PII) in public clouds acting as PII processors).

Communication between the Local eCREAM component and Central will take place after verification that the Local System is associated with the hospital network surveyed.

All interactions between the application and external systems, including system administrators, will be tracked on a log with data on system operations or incidents intercepted by the system, identifying any illicit access.

The system will employ a constantly active antivirus to verify the data being delivered.

Data received will be archived on databases whose file systems will be encrypted.

Archived data will be automatically backed up.

3.2. Integration protocols

Starting from the premise that data management is based on the principles of minimization and pseudonymization, three integration flows can be identified:

- For NLP Training:
 - From hospital database (EHR and RIS) to the Local eCREAM folders, by file transfer, in batch mode;
 - From local folders to the NLP training server, via secure data transfer, in batch mode.
- For Use Case 1:
 - From hospital database (EHR, LIS, and RIS) to the Local eCREAM folders, by file transfer, in batch mode;
 - From local folders to central folders, via secure data transfer, in batch mode.

- For Use Case 2:
 - From hospital database (EHR, LIS, and RIS) to the Local eCREAM database, via RESTful synchronous API;
 - From the local database to the central database, via RESTful synchronous API.

The secure data transfer from the Local eCREAM platform could be implemented in different ways, accordingly to the hospital policies:

- Secure FTP: Produced files can be transferred using Secure FTP (File Transfer Protocol), employing either FTPS (Secure FTP) or SFTP (SSH File Transfer Protocol), which apply data encryption during transfer.
- VPN: This allows file transfer over an insecure network, but by applying encryption to both connection points (source and destination), files can be placed in a shared folder with the necessary permissions.

4. Data flow and processing

The following paragraphs describe how the eCREAM platform will retrieve data for the NLP Training, UC1 and UC2 use cases.

It is defined that all the information will be transferred by the hospital using JSON structures specific for all the several types of data.

JSON is supported by a wide range of programming languages, facilitating the exchange, processing, and manipulation of data between heterogeneous systems. It is widely used in web APIs and RESTful services for transmitting data between the client and the server.

Given the type of data required to be extracted (repeatable, of various types, and with a complex structure), JSON has been chosen to allow for better management, ensuring an open and widely used standard.

For UC1, the use of CSV (Comma-Separated Values) file extractions is not excluded a priori. The CSV data format, a type of file format used to represent tabular data in plain text, separates data columns using commas, with each row representing a record. While commas are commonly used as delimiters, other characters like semicolons may be employed depending on local conventions.

However, CSV format has several disadvantages. It is limited in handling complex or nested data and in representing structured data. The lack of an official format may lead to differences in file interpretation, causing interoperability issues between systems. Additionally, characters such as commas in the text content could create ambiguities in file reading. The absence of semantic structure information has led to CSV not being the first choice for data export from individual entities.

Nevertheless, the CSV format is widely used for its simplicity and compatibility with many software and platforms. The decision to use it will depend on the nature of the data to be represented from individual entities and the feasibility of easy extraction.

4.1. NLP Training Use Case

The data will be exported through DB queries from the databases in text format. The texts will be included in files that can be xlsx or JSON, according to hospitals possibilities.

The hospital has to save these files in a file system that is shared with the local eCREAM components. The file system will contain a folder structure defined to organize content by source: EHR or RIS database.

Each textual information must be extracted reporting the unique emergency department episode identification code (episodeID), so that every piece of information related to the same patient/ED episode it's linked to the others.

Each extracted data will be organized according in a structure compliant with the data dictionary and saved in a JSON file.

Here below, it is reported the structure of the JSON messages extracted from the EHR and from the RIS database. The definition of each JSON entity is described in the document "Annex 2 – eCREAM Application Interface Specification".

Export from EHR database:

```
{
  "EpisodeID": "123441",
  "triageNotes": "abdominal pain since last night",
  "anamnesis": "Anamnesis",
  "allergiesTriage": "lactose",
  "clinicalExamination": "clinical exam",
  "knownPathologiesCollectedAtTriage": "known pathologies",
  "descriptionOfEventAtTriage": "Presence of gallstones",
  "otherTriageNotes": "none"
}
```

```

    "imagingTest": "text of image report",
    "vitalParameters": "vitalParameters",
    "homeBasedTherapy": "therapy at home",
    "clinicalDiary": "the patient performed the hygiene independently",
    "medicalVisit": "medicalVisit",
    "clinicalEDOutcome": "clinicalEDOutcome",
    "nursingNotes": "nursing notes",
    "diagnosisAtEndOfHospitalStay": "diagnosis",
    "dischargeNotes": "notes",
    "drugsTakenAtHome": "type of drugs",
    "clinicalConditionDischarge": "clinical conditions",
    "reportTextSpecialistConsultancy": "report of consultancy"
    "EDDischargeCarePlan": "EDDischargeCarePlan"
}

```

Export from RIS database:

```

{
    "EpisodeID": "123441",
    "RequestID": "5453532",
    "dateTimeRequestImagingTest": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
    "dateTimeImagingTestExecution": "2022-06-22T15:14:23",
    "dateTimeImagingTestReport": "2022-06-22T15:15:23",
    "imagingTestType": "rx chest",
    "imagingTestReportText": "No significant lesions are observed bony lesions of the skeletal segments under examination; presence of slight liquid stratum intra-articular coxofemoral on both sides."
}

```

Each file will be provided as input to the anonymization tool: a software service will extract the text from the file and provide it as the input of the tool. The tool will provide the anonymized output that will be saved by the service in a new file, that will be stored in a folder structure mirroring the one of the non-anonymized file.

The free text notes will be anonymised through the anonymization tool within the Local eCREAM platform. The anonymized text will be saved as txt files in specific local folders, where they will be stored until they are transferred to the Central eCREAM NLP server.

The following image shows the data flow.

NLP training

4.2. Use Case 1

The hospital will export a JSON file for each dataset related to the database involved in the data collection: EHR, LIS, RIS.

Each subset of data referring to an ED episode must report the ED episode identification code.

The JSON file will be saved by the hospital in three folders, corresponding to the three data sources, created in the shared file system within the local eCREAM platform. The definition of each JSON entity is described in the document "Annex 2 - Application Interface Specification".

Export from EHR database:

```
{
  "EpisodeID": "123441",
  "EDArrivalDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "sex": 1,
  "age": 35,
  "EDArrivalDateTime ": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "arrivalModeCode": 2
  "EDDateTime": {EDDateTime},
  "triage": {triage},
  "anamnesis": {anamnesis},
  "homeBasedTherapy": [{homeBasedTherapy}],
  "clinicalExamination": {clinicalExaminationDetection},
  "imagingText": [{imagingTestExecution}],
  "labTests": [{testExecutionLab}],
  "vitalParameters": [{vitalParametersDetection}],
  "nursingCareData": {nursingCareData},
  "cinicalDiary": [{cinicalDiary}],
  "medicalVisits": [{medicalVisits}],
  "specialistConsultancy": [{executionConsultation}],
  "discharge": {discharge},
  "ObsUnit": {ObsUnit},
  "followUp": {followUp}
}
```

Export from LIS database:

```
{
  "EpisodeID": "123441",
  "LabTest": glucose,
  "dateTimeRequestLabTest": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "dateTimeLabTestExecution": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "labTestResults": 100
  "unitOfMeasureLabTest": mg/dl
}
```

Export from RIS database:

```
{
  "EpisodeID": "123441",
  "RequestID": "5453532",
  "dateTimeRequestImagingTest": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "dateTimeImagingTestExecution": "2022-06-22T15:14:23",
  "dateTimeImagingTestReport": "2022-06-22T15:15:23",
  "imagingTestType": "rx chest",
  "imagingTestReportText": "No significant lesions are observed bony lesions of the skeletal segments under examination; presence of slight liquid stratum intra-articular coxofemoral on both sides."
}
```

After the JSON files are moved into the source folders, a software tool will extract the textual data from them and will use the anonymizer to obtain anonymized text. These texts will keep their linkage to the other pieces of information through the EpisodeID code.

The data will be then transferred to the eCREAM central components that:

- Will extract structured data from text with the use of the NLP tool
- Will perform the normalization of the data, unifying the codifications, the measure units and reporting the values to the same standards
- Will perform the calculation of the admission propensity.

In the following image, the UC1 data flow is depicted.

4.3. Use Case 2

Logistical information collected in the ED EHR will be transferred approximately in real-time (every 3 minutes) through integration APIs with JSON messages continuously, feeding a database of the Central eCREAM platform.

The information required for UC2 traces in real-time the events (visits, treatments, test, ...) of the ED episode during the patient's stay in the Emergency Department but will not contain any reference to the patient's personal identifiers.

The JSON message must be compliant with this structure:

Export from EHR database:

```
{
  "EpisodeID": "123441",
  "EDArrivalDateTime": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "EDArrivalDateTime ": "2022-06-22T15:13:23",
  "arrivalModeCode": 2
  "EDDateTime": {EDDateTime},
  "triage": {triage},
  "imagingText": [{imagingTestExecution}],
  "labTests": [{testExecutionLab}],
  "nursingCareData": {nursingCareData},
  "medicalVisits": [{medicalVisits}],
  "specialistConsultancy": [{executionConsultation}],
  "discharge": {discharge},
  "ObsUnit": {ObsUnit},
}
```

The definition of each JSON entity is described in the document "Annex 2 - Application Interface Specification".

Use Case 2

For real-time emergency department monitoring, to execute in UC2, data will be transferred via API between the hospital and a local eCREAM component. In the local platform, a service will perform data pre-processing, i.e. calculation of measures to be used in the statistical analysis of logistical data from logistical information, in order to anonymize the information and make it exportable outside the hospital facility. A further service will interoperate with the API of the central platform components to transmit the pre-processed data to the service that will calculate the monitoring indicators.